

INVESTIGATING A NOVEL MAGNESIUM RECOVERY MEMBRANE PROCESS

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INTRODUCTION

Most of the desalination plants worldwide are based on the reverse osmosis process, which produces drinking water and a concentrated solution of various salts. Disposal of this brine solution, similarly to disposal of landfill leachate, mining waters and others highly concentrated solutions in general, is linked with environmental difficulties, as they are in many cases simply released into the surroundings. If extraction of minerals dissolved in these solutions in valuable form was possible, not only environmental cost for their disposal could decrease, it could bring some new economic aspects to this, or even become a profitable part of the process [1].

One of the options how to achieve this is membrane crystallization. This emerging technology is funded on Donnan dialysis process [2] coupled with reactive crystallization/precipitation process. It has a lot of advantages in comparison with reactive crystallization, as it gives better control over the crystallization process, selected mass transfer, improved hydrodynamics and others, which, in the end, allow us to obtain crystals of high purity and narrower size distribution [3].

Membrane crystallization was already applied for magnesium recovery, by experiments with flat-sheet homogenous membranes [4]. Problems of this approach are low productivity (formation density) and significant scaling of the product in the membrane module, which is considered the most significant drawback of the process. According to the results of our experiments, conversion and formation density of product in hollow fibres membrane module highly exceeded possibilities of flat-sheet ion-exchange membranes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, such a promising process was applied in experiments to obtain $Mg(OH)_2$ from solutions of $MgCl_2$ and $NaOH$, flowing on the opposite sides of the anion-exchange hollow-fibres. Hollow-fibre membrane modules with various number of fibres were used with $MgCl_2$ solution flowing on the lumen side and $NaOH$ solution flowing on the shell side of hollow-fibres.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mentioned advantages of membrane crystallization have been confirmed, as by modulations of concentration of used solutions and their flow rates we were able to cause increase or decrease of ion transfer – this is, in accordance with our observation, the most important characteristic of the process, as conversion and crystal size are dependent on the amount of transferred ions. Co-current and counter-current flow were compared as well, in favour of co-current flow – this type of mutual flow had a much higher conversion rate, exceeding the conversion rate of counter-current flow by 20%.

Apart from this, the hollow fibres membrane module has more feasible options for scaling reduction in comparison with flat-sheet membranes. In the experiments, glass beads were used as an abrasive, with partial success – the amount of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ in the solution was 2.5 times higher than in the experiments without the glass beads. Still, more than 90% of the product remained in the module, as scaled particles.

To evaluate the feasibility of this process in desalination plants, artificial brine solutions have been prepared and used as the source of Mg^{2+} – purity of crystals obtained from brine solutions were different, depending on the brine solution composition. Brine with a low amount of Ca^{2+} proved to be more usable, with the purity of synthesised crystals above 98.6%, which confirms the high economic potential of process, as the price per ton of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ highly depends on its purity.

Usage of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as a much cheaper source of $(\text{OH})^-$ ions proved to be highly ineffective – despite the conversion of the process, calculated from Mg^{2+} concentrations, was above 30%, a significant part of the product remained inside of a module, in form of scaling.

Keywords: brine disposal, membrane crystallization, hollow-fibres, $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$

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